

GRP MITRED PIPE BEND

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A mitred pipe bend of GRP has been tested in order to investigate its reactions to loading with internal pressure and with a bending moment. In literature attention is paid to stresses and deformation of mitred pipe bends. The sample investigated appears to behave qualitatively as predicted in this literature. The quantitative agreement is less satisfactory. The reasons for this difference are explained.

Strains in the wall and displacements of the free end of the investigated bend have been measured. During the investigation the wall thickness has been doubled by adding extra layers to the laminate. Afterwards the wall thickness has been further increased locally. The effect of this increase on strains and displacements is reported and discussed. Especially the local increase of the thickness of the laminate appears to be useful in order to arrive at a well-balanced construction of the bend.

In many process installations piping systems made of glass reinforced polyester or epoxy (GRP) are used in order to cope with the demands, put forward by the process medium. Even more than in the case of steel piping, the calculation of expansions is of great importance for GRP piping systems. In this respect it is necessary to dispose of data regarding the stiffness of and the stresses in the elements of such systems.

An important element of each piping system is a pipe bend. In the case of GRP the usual design is a mitred bend. A bend, as well as a branching, is a sensitive element in a piping system. Because of its shape greater wall stresses as well as larger deformations than in straight piping parts are to be expected under normal loads. This raises the question of optimising the design of the bend; not only the required strength but also its functioning as a part of the piping system are to be considered.

An investigation has been made of a mitred pipe bend of GRP (fig. 1) in order to acquire an insight into its characteristics and to find possible ways to improve its design.

Fig. 1 - The mitred pipe bend investigated.

Only one sample has been tested but during the investigation the wall thickness has been increased twice, in order to investigate the effect of a full and the effect of a local increase of the wall thickness. The purpose was to get an orientation of the problems involved; a further investigation with other samples will be necessary in order to draw more detailed conclusions and indications for a proper design of the bend.

Within the scope of this investigation the pipe bend has to satisfy two requirements: 1. sufficient strength in relation to its mechanical loading; 2. a proper performance of its function as a part of the piping system.

The mechanical loading, mentioned in the first demand, is caused by internal pressure and by forces and bending moments, acting on the flanges. These forces and moments are caused by various in- and external influences in the piping system. During the investigation the condition has been added, that nowhere in the wall the strain should be allowed to exceed $\epsilon = 0,2\%$ (ref. 1).

The second demand implicates, that the stiffness of the bend must be known, while additionally the deformations caused by variations in pressure, temperature and other loads should be known. On this basis optimization of stiffness and deformations by structural means may be undertaken.

In this investigation no attention has been paid to variations in temperature and ensuing expansion problems. Our first intention was to find the relation between variations in pressure and the moment acting on the flanges. The basis of this relationship is that a bend will deform upon the application of internal pressure. This deformation consists of a displacement and of a rotation of the flanges with regard to each other. The displacements are small in general and will rarely lead to problems. The angular rotation, however, generally introduces a bending moment in the system. To illustrate this we consider the system of figure 2.

Fig. 2 - Part of a piping system.

As a result of the application of a pressure p the free flange of the bend AB has the tendency to rotate over an angle $-\alpha$. This, however, is impeded by the support at C which allows a horizontal but not a vertical displacement ($f_c = 0$). This introduces the reaction force F_c . Under the condition mentioned

the magnitude of F_c can be calculated (see fig. 3):

Fig. 3 - Deformation of the elements of fig. 2 as a function of various loads.

$$f_c = \alpha_p \cdot l + f_p + \alpha_M \cdot l + f_M + \alpha_F \cdot l + f_F + f_l = 0 \quad \dots(1)$$

With the elastic constants as defined in figure 3 we obtain

$$\frac{p \cdot l}{c_1} + \frac{p}{c_2} + \frac{M \cdot l}{c_3} + \frac{M}{c_4} + \frac{F_c \cdot l}{c_5} + \frac{F_c}{c_6} + \frac{F_c \cdot l^3}{c_7} = 0 \quad \dots(2)$$

If l is not too small the second, fourth, fifth and sixth term may be neglected, compared to the other terms. The bending moment at B equals $M = F_c \cdot l$. Consequently the internal pressure p generates in the bend of figure 2 a bending moment M , approximately amounting to

$$M(1/c_3 + l^2/c_7) = - p l / c_1 \quad \dots(3)$$

If the rotation $-\alpha$ at B would be totally suppressed by a moment M , this should have the magnitude

$$M = - p \cdot c_3 / c_1 \quad \dots(4)$$

The value of c_1 is negative generally. Its magnitude can be influenced by the design of the bend. If we choose the design in such a manner, that the value of $1/c_1$ approaches zero as nearly as possible, we diminish the load on the bend, thereby reducing the strength requirements in service. It is therefore of importance, that we determine in our investigation the magnitude of c_1 and c_2 , because this provides us with data on an internal cause of moments in the piping system.

Besides we shall determine the local stresses in the bend, caused by internal pressure and external moment analytically as well as experimentally. This may help us to optimize the wall thickness.

Finally the second demand implicates, that we make measurements from which the constants $c_3 \dots c_6$ can be determined.

3. Theory

3.1 As a first approximation the bend can be described as a smooth bend according to figure 4.

Fig. 4 - Smooth bend

The tangential stress (σ_t) at the outer- ($\phi=180^\circ$) and inner- ($\phi=0^\circ$) curvature of the bend, arising from an internal pressure (p) is according to Schwaigerer (ref. 2) (see fig. 5):

$$\phi = 180^\circ \rightarrow \sigma_t = \frac{p \cdot d}{2 \cdot s} \frac{2R + d/2}{2R + d + s} \quad \dots(5)$$

$$\phi = 0^\circ \rightarrow \sigma_t = \frac{p \cdot d}{2 \cdot s} \frac{2R - d/2}{2R - d - s} \quad \dots(6)$$

Fig. 5 - Loads on and stresses in a smooth bend

For a load of $p = 0.4 \text{ N/mm}^2$ on a bend with $R = 500 \text{ mm}$, $d = 498 \text{ mm}$, $s = 6.4 \text{ mm}$ we find

$$\phi = 180^\circ \rightarrow \sigma_t = 15.6 \times 0.83 = 12.9 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

$$\phi = 0^\circ \rightarrow \sigma_t = 15.6 \times 1.52 = 23.6 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

From this it appears, that the stresses are higher at the inner curvature of the bend (see the spot indicated with 1 in fig. 5). This is also to be expected for the mitred bend. This suggests the use of an extra reinforcing laminate around the $\phi = 0$ area of the bend.

Loading with a positive bending moment M (fig. 5) produces tensile- and bending stresses at different places in the wall of the bend. The highest combination of stresses appears at the $\phi = 90^\circ$ area and directed tangentially (see the spot indicated with 2 in fig. 5). According to Schwaigerer (ref. 2) the magnitude amounts to:

$$\phi = 90^\circ \rightarrow \sigma_t = \frac{32 M \cdot (d + 2 \cdot s)}{\pi (d + 2 \cdot s)^4 - d^4} \cdot D \quad \dots(7)$$

D is a function of R , d and s ; in our case it equals about 1. With the above mentioned dimensions and a load $M = 400 \text{ Nm}$ we find

$$\phi = 90^\circ \rightarrow \sigma_t = 0.32 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

As this load is characteristic for the moments on such a bend, the stresses

resulting from it can be neglected.

3.2 Murthy (ref. 3) presents formulae for the stresses around the intersection of two parts (i.e. the seam) of a mitred bend. He assumes a constant wall thickness and an isotropic material. Though neither condition is fulfilled in our case, we still present the course of the axial and tangential stresses along three lines parallel to the axis at the outer surface, calculated according to Murthy's formulae (fig. 6).

It is apparent from figure 6 that we may expect high stress peaks at the seam, which, however, are damped out at some distance of it.

3.3 Jones and Kitching (ref. 4) present formulae for the stresses in and the deformation of the walls of the mitred bend and for the rotation α of the free flange as a result of an applied bending moment M . We will not go into these formulae here as we may expect from equation (7) that these stresses will be rather low. We may check this suggestion experimentally.

It may be expected that the stresses measured at the sample will differ from the results of the calculations based on the equations given above. Main causes of the differences are:

- a. differences in wall thickness, caused by the manual application of the laminates, the cutting of the laminates and the extra strengthening of the seams and other places.
- b. the influence of the stiffened end flange and of the other seam in the bend on the local stresses. Any stiffening reduces the local deformations and therefore influences the stress-pattern.
- c. the anisotropy of the material.
- d. the composition of the wall of two layers of different materials: PVC and GRP.
- e. possible deviation of the roundness of the sections.

In view of the objectives of this investigation - a first orientation on the function and the design of the bend - a more detailed theoretical analysis was considered unnecessary.

Fig. 6 - Stress according to Murthy at the outer surface of a mitred bend ($d=498$ mm, $s=6.4$ mm) loaded with a pressure of 0.4 N/mm^2 .

The bend has been designed according to figure 1. The wall has been built up on an inner layer of 3 mm thick PVC sheet (which consequently serves as mold) on which layers of glass fibre mat (450 g/m^2) and textile glass fabric (800 g/m^2) impregnated with polyester resin based on isophthalic acid have been applied according to figure 7. The laminate had a glass content of about 40% by weight.

Fig. 7 - Building-up of the wall of PVC liner and GRP laminate (1, 2, 3). Next to the figure the order is mentioned in which mat (m) and fabric (f) have been applied. The layers 2 and 3 have been applied successively in later stages of the investigation.

The tests were performed in three series: In series I only the PVC liner and GRP layer 1 were present; in series II GRP layer 2 had been added; in series III GRP layer 3 had been added, but only in the region of $-60^\circ < \phi < +60^\circ$ (see fig. 9). Each of the three parts of the mitred bend has been covered with layers of mat and fabric in such a way, that these layers overlap at both sides of the seams of the bend for 100 ... 300 mm. Because of this the wall thickness at the seams is twice as high as appears from fig. 7.

Strain gauges were fixed at various selected places on the outside as well as on the PVC inner surface. Gauges and rosettes with a filament length of 20 mm have been used. Upon the lamination for a new series (II or III) on the spot of the old ones new gauges were fixed on the new outer surface. This made it possible to measure the strain on the chosen places at both sides of the wall.

Additionally the total deformation of the bend has been measured. One of these measurements was the displacement of the free end of the bend using

dial gauges as indicated in figure 8. From these measurements the rotation α and the displacement f according to figure 3 can be derived.

The bend was installed according to figure 8. It could be subjected to an internal pressure p , a bending moment $M = F_1 \times e$, a lateral force F_2 or combinations of these. In view of the application of the internal pressure the bend was filled with oil. For the application of the forces F_1 and F_2 a beam had been fixed to the free flange.

5. Measuring results

5.1 Young's modulus.

In preliminary measurements the Young's modulus of a laminate with the same structure as layer 1 (fig. 7) has been determined. On this basis we assume that the modulus of the material of the bend amounts to 9500 N/mm^2 . The manual manufacturing of the wall resulted, especially at the seams, in such a position of the layers of fabric, that the assumption of isotropic behaviour of the material is justified, with a Poisson's ratio of $\nu = 0.25$.

5.2 Strain measurements.

The strains have been measured as a function of both the internal pressure p and the applied bending moment M , or a combination of both. A regression analysis according to $\epsilon_c = ap + bM$ was applied to the measured strains

Fig. 8 - Set-up of the loading with bending moment ($F_1 \times e$) and lateral force (F_2) and of the measurement of the displacements of the free end.

ϵ_m of each strain gage. This made it possible to determine the values of the strain ϵ_c at the strain gauges for chosen reference values of p (0.4 N/mm^2) and M (400 Nm). In nearly all measuring series such regression lines for ϵ_c were found, that the standard deviation $\sqrt{\sum(\epsilon_c - \epsilon_m)^2 / (n-2)}$ exceeded only rarely the value of 25×10^{-6} .

In applying the loads care was taken that at no place the strain would exceed 2×10^{-3} (0,2%). Within this limit no interaction of pressure and moment regarding the strain could be ascertained. We therefore may regard the results of pressure and moment separately.

In loading with a moment of 400 Nm , at no place a strain of 10^{-4} or higher was found. In view of this order of magnitude a further consideration of the strains as a function of the bending moment appears not to be worthwhile.

Fig. 9 - Location of the third GRP layer and of some of the strain gauges (+).

The strain at an internal pressure of $p = 0.4 \text{ N/mm}^2$ (as calculated with the above regression formulae) for points along the sections AB and CD (see fig. 9) is reproduced in the figures 10 and 11. In these figures the tangential and axial strains are given, as derived from gauges at the inner or outer wall surface.

If we compare figure 10 with calculations according to Murthy (ref. 3), we find in the first instance a qualitative agreement, but the course of the curves shows clearly the effect of the wall being homogeneous nor of constant thickness. For this reason no attempt has been made to compare the measured strain through calculation with the wall stress according to Murthy for those places.

Fig. 10 - Tangential and axial strains along the section AB at a pressure of 0.4 N/mm^2 for each of the series I, II and III. The tangential strains ϵ_{tang} have been measured in the plane of the section AB, the axial strains ϵ_{ax} parallel to the axis of the middle part of the bend.

We can, however, compare the magnitude of the measured strains with the strains in a straight pipe with the same wall structure as series I. Using for GRP: $E = 9500 \text{ N/mm}^2$, $\nu = 0.25$ and for PVC: $E = 3000 \text{ N/mm}^2$, $\nu = 0.38$ we find by calculation $\epsilon_{\text{tang}} = 1.23 \times 10^{-3}$; $\epsilon_{\text{ax}} = 0.33 \times 10^{-3}$. This is indeed of the same order of magnitude as the data in figure 11. The course of ϵ in figure 11, however, shows that e.g. the bending stresses, caused by the mitred connection at the seam AB, have not yet damped out in section CD.

Fig. 11 - Tangential and axial strains along the section CD at a pressure of 0.4 N/mm^2 for each of the series I, II and III.

5.3 Deformation measurements.

The deformation measurements have been performed with varying pressure, moment and lateral force. From these measurements the elastic constants according to figure 3 have been calculated (see table 1).

Table 1. Elastic constants according to figure 3

Series	c_1	c_2	c_3	c_4	c_5	c_6
I	- 555	- 0.50	0.81×10^9	1.32×10^6	$1,16 \times 10^3$	1.82×10^3
II	- 833	- 0.72	1.09×10^9	1.92×10^6	1.70×10^6	2.71×10^3
III	+ 8333	- 1.65	1.35×10^9	2.31×10^6	2.32×10^6	3.33×10^3
	N/mm ²	N/mm ³	N.mm	N	N	N/mm

With combinations of loads by pressure, moment and lateral force the deformation was about the same as the sum of the deformations found for each of these loads separately. So no interaction between the different kinds of loading has been observed. This confirms our expectation: In view of the ratio of wall thickness to diameter (for series III: $21/492 = 0,043$) of the tested bend, non linear effects were unlikely.

In accordance with formula (4) we now calculate the moment required to suppress fully the rotation α at a pressure of 0.4 N/mm^2 . We find for
series I : $M = 585 \text{ Nm}$
series II : $M = 525 \text{ Nm}$
series III: $M = - 65 \text{ Nm}$

6. Conclusions

From Murthy's analysis of the influence of internal pressure (ref. 3) it appears clearly, that the strains rise strongly near the seams, especially at the inner side of the bend. This gives a strong indication - which was realised in the sample tested - to increase the wall thickness considerably near the seams. On the basis of theory (compare figure 6) increasing the local wall thickness by a factor 2 at the outer curvature, and by a factor 3 at the inner curvature of the bend seems a reasonable line of action.

Also from theory (ref. 2) indications to increase the wall thickness at

the inner curvature (around $\phi=0$) of the bend only can be derived. The effect of this was checked in series III (see fig. 9). An overall increase of the wall thickness lowers the stresses near the seams and on other places. A local increase of the wall thickness at the inner curvature of the bend, however, apparently results in a more efficient utilization of the extra material.

The strain measurements show, that with the manual application of the laminate without more one cannot reach a dependable and smooth shape of the stresses in the wall: the measurements show variations of the strain that do not correspond with a regular build-up of the wall and a predictable behaviour. We may, however, expect that this will improve considerably if the application is done according to an exactly prepared drawing.

The influence of a bending moment on the bend is small. A moment will cause unroundness of the section (ref. 4). This leads on one hand to a low stiffness c_3 and c_4 and on the other hand to bending stresses at more than one place in the wall section. As appears from our measurements the latter are small at $M = 400 \text{ Nm}$. Though higher moments are not inconceivable in piping systems, loading with a moment does not appear to be an important criterion for the design of a mitred bend like the one tested.

Table I provides information on the stiffness of the bend. Increasing of the overall wall thickness results in an increase of the stiffness, though considerably less than proportional. Much more effective is again the local increase of the thickness at the inner curvature of the bend. In series III the latter even caused the sign of c_1 to change. There apparently is a certain value for this increase (in our case slightly smaller than that applied in series III) for which $1/c_1$ becomes very small. In such a case the internal pressure will not induce a rotation α and therefore not a bending moment either.

For the design of a bend it might, however, not be of high importance to aim at $1/c_1 = 0$, in view of the subordinate influence of the moment on the wall stresses. It seems of higher importance to use the local increase of the wall thickness for lowering the wall stresses caused directly by internal pressure.

7.

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8.

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9.

Nomenclature

Nomenclature of symbols not explained in the same chapter.

- ϵ_c strain, calculated from a series of strain measurements under different conditions
- ϵ_m strain, measured under certain conditions with the aid of strain gauges
- ν Poisson's ratio
- ϕ angular coordinate indicating the place in the wall of the bend (see fig. 5 and 6)
- $c_1 \dots c_6$ elastic constants of the bend, as defined in figure 3
- E Young's modulus
- axial directed parallel to the local position of the axis in the pipe bend
- tangential directed tangential to the wall, perpendicular to the local axis of the pipe bend.

SESSION 16:
FABRICATION METHODS

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